

DIGITAL ETIQUETTE AWARENESS ON SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS AMONG MALAYSIAN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Tahirah Mt Tahir

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Abstract

The main aim of this study is to identify the level of digital etiquette awareness on social media platforms among Malaysian primary school students. A survey method was chosen to conduct the study among students from 7 to 12 years old in primary school. The results of this study indicate that the level of digital etiquette awareness among students were positive based on the feedback of scenario about social media activities such as photo or video uploads, online video watching, online chatting and commenting on social networking sites. However, there are some students does not aware with the right digital etiquette during online. Further study should be undertaken to determine the suitable solution to increase the level of digital etiquette awareness.

1 INTRODUCTION

The term ‘Digital Etiquette’ encompasses Netiquette, Cyberethics, Online Ethics and Internet Ethics. The idea of ‘Netiquette’ can broadly defined as the practice of moral and ethical values among users during online [1]. These definition are close to those of [2] and [3] who define ‘Cyberethics’ as rules or guidelines that afforded for the behaviour of people in Internet environment and the moral choices during the use of Internet technologies and digital media by individuals. Whereas, [4] used the term ‘Internet ethics’ to describe the

expressions or way people should behave during using the Internet. In this study, the term ‘Digital Etiquette’ will be use to refer to the proper use of digital media (social media platforms) coupled with an effective moral duties and responsibilities among users during the Internet use. The importance of support and guidance to the students in terms of rules of online etiquette is needed although the rules or laws of social media sites environment are still being defined [5]. The digital etiquette that we have identified therefore assists in our understanding of the role of digital etiquette awareness that applied on social media usage among children.

The increasing of social media usage among Australian children from 11 to 12 years old shows by 59% of them have social networking site profile [6]. 31% of children in Thailand from 6 to 12 years old have at least one account of social networking site [7]. Internet users survey by Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission (MCMC) in 2017 has found that Malaysian Internet users among 5 to 17 years old are 83.2%. Social media usage is among the top online activities in that group [8]. However, the increasing of social media platforms usage among children may influence them with some issues. New ethics issues have raise with the development and usage of ICTs and leads into unethical actions as many issues involve in social media [9]. In a national survey report 2014 [10] among Malaysian primary school students on staying safe online, there is a

question asked to the children about rules on discipline, safety, etiquette and supervision by a parent or guardian. The results found that only 33% of children were indicated that there is rules for etiquette and 30% of them were chosen to practice good Internet etiquette from the 12 steps of action taken to protect them on the Internet. It is essential to improve the usage starting from elementary school by proper use of Internet that respect to codes of conduct [4]. However, the practices of etiquette on social media platforms have not been adequately researched. Thus, the level of digital etiquette awareness on social media platforms among Malaysian primary school students needs to identify before proceeds with appropriate solution. The results of this study is use to explore the knowledge and skills of digital etiquette awareness.

2 PROPOSED WORK

The following is a sample table. Please adhere to the table format and caption. A quantitative approach was chosen in this study to identify the level of digital etiquette awareness. The quantitative approach provides statistical results to discuss the action taken from scenario by percentage. The questionnaire was designed in a scenario-based question with multiple-choice answers for each question. There are four scenarios that examine the participant’s response towards an online situation or environment. The scenarios are created based on the social media activities to identify their level of digital etiquette awareness. Participants were then required to provide feedback based on the scenarios. Each scenario has questions that highlight the respondent’s reaction on the simulated situations. The survey was distributed by the researcher among 218 primary school students between the ages of 7 to 12 years old at rural and city areas within the states of Kedah and Penang and 210 of questionnaires was collected. The findings will help to provide

guidelines for further research related to children behavior towards digital etiquette.

3 RESULTS

Scenario 1 is based on identifying problematic user-generated content which the situation of posting inappropriate photo or video in social media platform such as Facebook and YouTube without someone else’s knowledge. Students are asked about the action from people who upload the photo or video. As shown in Table I, most of the students are able to identify the required action. However, some of the students that chosen other than the required action may not know or does not have enough knowledge about the consequences of posting inappropriate photo or video.

Table 1 : Uploading Photo and Video

Question	Scenario 1	
	Action	Percentage
If you were Sara, what would you do to resolve this situation?	Take out the photo or video	82.1
	Doesn’t take any action	14.2
	Others	3.7

Scenario 2 is based on exposure to potentially harmful content and encountering violent material content. The situation is about watching online video such as in YouTube and there is advertisement about the lists of violence anime. It involves weapon fights that result in bodily harm, deaths or dangerous explosions. The question asks about the action taken whether to watch the video or not. Table II shows that event though the percentage of not watching the violence video is quite high. Surprisingly some of them want to continue watching the video and do not know to give feedback. The reason is they may not have enough knowledge about harmful and violence content.

Table 2 : Watching Online Video

Question	Scenario 2	
	Action	Percentage
What would you do if you were Ali?	Continue to watch the video	25.7
	Doesn't watch the video	71.1
	Don't know	3.2

Scenario 3 is about communicated with strangers. The situation is created about communication with strangers through social networking. Question number one asks about the first reaction that the respondents have when strangers contact them on social network. Question number two is to identify whether respondents know how to block strangers on social network. The third question is whether the participants want to add the strangers to their friend list or not. The last question asks about action taken if the strangers ask for personal information. Table III shows that not more than 50% are aware to block the strangers. It is somewhat surprising that they do not apply the function to react in the situation even though more than half was know how to use it in social networks. A possible explanation for this might be that the students were uncertain to use the knowledge of block function and more comfortable to tell someone or keep quiet. Though the number that chooses to add contacts from strangers is small but it needs to be taken seriously to avoid any potential risks.

Scenario four is about cyber bullying risk. The situation of posting negative comments towards photo posted on social networking page is created. The first question is the awareness of negative comment report. Question number two is the awareness of selecting the audience for viewing the photo and the last question is about reaction towards accessing the photos. The results show that more than half of the students

do not aware with report negative comment function in social network and to select audience who can view photo. Though the students were able to identify required action for not posting negative comment but one unanticipated finding was that there were some of them chosen to act as cyber bully.

As a conclusion, the level of digital etiquette awareness among primary school students is positive but there are some students tend to choose wrong actions to react based on the scenario.

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